

New Milne-type Inequalities for Lipschitzian Functions by Conformable Fractional Operators

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DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.18017673](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18017673)

Abstract

In this paper, new Milne-type inequalities are proved by conformable fractional operators for Lipschitzian functions. Moreover, some results are presented by using specific functions and suitable parameters of the obtained theorem. This shows how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar inequalities. Furthermore, these results may be further generalized by examining other classes of convex functions or by employing different fractional integral operators.

Keywords: Milne-type inequalities, Lipschitzian functions, Conformable fractional operators.

1 Introduction

Many mathematicians have investigated numerical integration formulas and their corresponding error bounds using various analytical methods. In this context, numerous mathematical inequalities have been established for different classes of functions, such as convex, bounded, and Lipschitz functions. For instance, Dragomir and Agarwal [1] derived error bounds for the trapezoidal inequalities by employing the properties of convex functions. In another study, Dragomir [2] is introduced Simpson-type inequalities and examined their applications to quadrature formulas within numerical analysis. Moreover, Budak et al. [3] studied several forms of Simpson-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions in the framework of generalized fractional integrals.

The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule, commonly known as Simpson's second rule, has a significant role in numerical integration. Since it employs three-point quadratic kernels, these formulas are often referred to as Newton-type results. Milne-type inequalities can be viewed as extensions of Newton-type formulas, using higher-order or generalized kernels to achieve better approximation accuracy. Recently, several studies have focused on deriving and extending Milne-type inequalities by using convexity properties and fractional integral operators, which provide wider applications in numerical analysis. For instance, in [4], some error bounds for Newton-type inequalities in numerical integration have been established by employing convex

functions. Likewise, certain Newton-type inequalities based on convexity are presented in [5], along with applications to specific cases of real functions. Several new estimates of Milne's quadrature rule have been derived by Djenaoui and Meftah [6], particularly for functions whose first derivative is s -convex. The paper [7] presents error bounds for Milne-type inequalities applied to functions of bounded variation. Moreover, in [8], fractional Milne-type inequalities are derived using differentiable convex functions. For more details, the reader is referred to the paper [9].

2 Preliminaries

Let us put forth some preliminaries which will be utilized in the sequel.

- i. Simpson's quadrature formula (Simpson's 1/3 rule) is formulated as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

- ii. Simpson's second formula or Newton-Cotes quadrature formula (Simpson's 3/8 rule (cf. [10])) is formulated as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Formulae (1) and (2) are provided for any function f with continuous 4th derivative on $[a, b]$.

The most popular Newton-Cotes quadrature involving three-point is Simpson-type inequality is as follows:

Theorem 2.1. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then one has the following inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

One of the classical closed type quadrature rules is the Simpson 3/8 rule based on the Simpson 3/8 inequality as follows:

Theorem 2.2 (See [10]). If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

By using the Newton-Cotes formulas, the Milne's formula which is of open type is parallel to the Simpson's formula which is of closed type, since they are held under the same conditions.

Theorem 2.3 (See [11]). Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a four times continuously differentiable mapping on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a, b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7(b-a)^4}{23040} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty. \quad (3)$$

For building our main results, the main definitions of Riemann-Liouville integrals and conformable integrals, which are well known in the literature, are presented as follows:

Definition 2.1. The gamma function, beta function, and incomplete beta function are defined

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt,$$

$$\mathfrak{B}(x, y) := \int_0^1 t^{x-1} (1-t)^{y-1} dt,$$

and

$$\mathcal{B}(x, y, r) := \int_0^r t^{x-1} (1-t)^{y-1} dt,$$

respectively for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Definition 2.2 (See [12]). The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\beta f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f(x)$ of order $\beta > 0$ are given by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (4)$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (5)$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals equals to the classical integrals for the case of $\beta = 1$.

Jarad et al. investigated the fractional conformable integral operators in paper [13]. They also provided certain characteristics and relationships between these operators and several other fractional operators. The fractional conformable integral operators are defined as follows:

Definition 2.3 (See [13]). The fractional conformable integral operator ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\beta \in \mathbb{C}$, $Re(\beta) > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ are described by

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^\alpha - (t-a)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t > a \quad (6)$$

and

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^\alpha - (b-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t < b, \quad (7)$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$.

If we choose $\alpha = 1$, then the fractional integral in (6) and (7) coincides with the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral in (4) and (5), respectively. Some recent results according to fractional integral inequalities, see [15, 16] and the references cited therein.

3 An essential identity

Lemma 3.1 (See [14]). Let us note that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \quad (8) \\ & = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \sum_{i=1}^4 I_i, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_2 &= \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_3 &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_4 &= \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt. \end{aligned} \right.$$

4 Milne-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions

In this section, we consider some Milne-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions by using conformable fractional integrals.

Theorem 4.1. Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 3.1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) \\ & \quad + 2\Omega_7(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_8(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \left[\mathfrak{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1 \right) - \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) \right], \\ \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| dt = \frac{1}{4\alpha^\beta} - \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^\alpha \right), \end{array} \right.$$

and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| t dt \\ = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \left[\mathfrak{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1 \right) - \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) - \mathfrak{B} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}, \beta + 1 \right) + \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) \right] \\ \Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| t dt, \\ \Omega_7(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| t dt, \\ \Omega_8(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| t dt \\ = \frac{7}{32\alpha^\beta} - \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \left[\mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) - \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) \right]. \end{array} \right.$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 3.1 and since f' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_b^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_a^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| = \left| \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \right. \\ & \left. \times \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left[\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \Bigg\} \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right. \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \\
 & \left. + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right\} \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| L(1-2t)(b-a) dt \right. \\
 & \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| L(1-2t)(b-a) dt \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \Bigg\} = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \\
& \times \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) \\
& + 2\Omega_7(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_8(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) \}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 4.1. By taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4.1, the following Milne-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2(b-a)^\beta} [J_{a+}^\beta f(b) + J_{b-}^\beta f(a)] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} L \{ \Omega_1(1, \beta) - 2\Omega_5(1, \beta) + \Omega_2(1, \beta) - 2\Omega_6(1, \beta) \\
& + 2\Omega_7(1, \beta) - \Omega_3(1, \beta) + 2\Omega_8(1, \beta) - \Omega_4(1, \beta) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

This is established by Hezenci and Budak in paper [17, Theorem 5].

Remark 4.2. Let us consider $\beta = 1$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4.1. Then, the following Milne-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} L.$$

This is established by Hezenci and Budak in paper [17, Corollary 4]. This inequality helps us to establish the error bound for Milne's rule.

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